

Performance and Transient-Resiliency of S- and E-band Upgrades of a C+L-band System

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Abstract: This work analyses two possible band upgrades to a C+L-band system: S- or E-band. The systems (with and without Raman amplification) are compared regarding performance and the magnitude of power transients generated by link faults. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Space division multiplexing (SDM) and multi-band transmission (MBT) are promising technologies for increasing the bandwidth of current optical transport networks. SDM techniques such as multi-core or multi-mode fibers, incur high capital expenditure (CAPEX) due to the need for new fiber deployment. A more cost-effective option is multi-fiber transmission by activating unused (dark) fibers. However, if no dark fibers are available, the CAPEX for multi-fiber transmission may be prohibitive [1]. MBT, which aims to expand the transmission band of existing fibers beyond the C band (as shown in Fig. 1a), becomes a more attractive solution when fiber deployment costs are high or when extensive fiber deployment is required to realize SDM [2].

Expanding transmission bands beyond the C and L bands presents several challenges, including performance imbalances, higher component costs, and possible issues with survivability and protection [3]. For instance, increased fiber loss, higher amplifier noise figures (NF), and power transfer due to stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) contribute to significant performance disparities between transmission bands [4]. Moreover, amplifiers and other components specific to these new bands will likely be more expensive due to lower demand and reduced efficiency.

The extensive spectral occupation of a beyond C+L-band system, exceeding 13 THz, increases power transfer between wavelengths due to SRS. SRS creates interdependencies between wavelengths and can lead to power transients following a link failure, posing additional challenges for service survivability and network management. To mitigate these issues, implementing a 14-THz guard band between transmission bands has been shown to reduce wavelength interdependencies [5], and simplify network operations, despite sacrificing performance by not utilizing spectral regions with the lowest fiber attenuation. Moreover, Raman amplification can help balance power between transmission bands and improve the spectral efficiency (SE) of MBT systems [6].

In this work, we employ numerical simulations to explore the advantages of using the E-band over the S-band to upgrade a C+L-band system. Unlike previous works, which focus solely on the different impacts of SRS on system performance and capacity, our study also analyzes how the choice of the additional transmission band affects the expected impact of power transients caused by link faults in MBT systems with contiguous bandwidths of up to 18 THz. We examine scenarios both with and without Raman amplification.

Fig. 1. (a) Frequency-dependent fiber loss and nonlinear coefficient, (b) frequency bounds of each amplification band used in this work, and (c) Telefónica national reference network topology.

2. Power Optimization Framework Description and Link Fault Simulation

We assume each amplification band spans 6 THz (as shown in Fig. 1b) and 120-GBd signals are transmitted within a 150-GHz spectral grid, resulting in 40 channels per band. We evaluate three transmission systems: C+L, S+C+L, and E+C+L. Each system can utilize up to 20 backward Raman pumps. For the C+L-band system, Raman pumps are placed within the 199 THz to 218 THz range, while for the S+C+L-band system, they are placed between 205 THz and 224 THz. For the E+C+L-band system, we consider two pump placement strategies: (i) Diverse Pumping (div-pump), with a maximum of 10 pumps placed between 199 THz and 208 THz, and another 10 pumps between 221 THz and 230 THz; and (ii) Grouped Pumping (group-pump), in which all twenty pumps are placed between 219 THz and 238 THz to prevent E-band power depletion.

Proper optimization (launch power and Raman pump) is crucial to obtain the best performance of MBT systems due to the frequency-varying behavior of components' characteristics, and the SRS effect. We apply a multi-objective genetic algorithm to simultaneously optimize the launch power and design the Raman amplifier [6] with two concurrent objectives: maximize the system capacity and minimize the sum of the GSNR variation per band. The nonlinear interference contribution to the GSNR is calculated using the Generalized Gaussian Noise (GGN) model, and the SRS is calculated by numerically solving the Raman equations (both algorithms are available in the open-source Python library GNPY [7]). The ideal single-span system capacity is the sum of the capacity of all transmitted channels, given by $2 \cdot R_S \cdot \log_2(1 + \text{GSNR}_i)$ for channel i , where R_S is the symbol rate. The optimization is performed in a single 80-km span and amplifier setup with the same characteristics as in [6].

To estimate the impact of power transients caused by SRS, we conduct link fault simulations using the Telefónica national reference network (Fig. 1c), following the methodology outlined in [3]. To simplify the optimization, we assume all network spans are uniform, each measuring 80 km. This network is also utilized to calculate the network-wide average channel capacity, following the methodology described in [8].

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2a presents the non-dominated solutions computed by the optimization algorithm. When examining capacity values for solutions with an average $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 0.5$ dB, the baseline C+L-band system is the least favorable in terms of total ideal capacity due to the limited number of channels and the absence of Raman pumps.

We first compare three upgrade options for the C+L-band system: adding Raman pumps, deploying the S-band, or deploying the E-band. Notably, the E+C+L-band system without Raman amplification and the C+L-band system with Raman amplification exhibit similar total capacities. In contrast, the S+C+L-band system without Raman pumps achieves a 10.8% higher capacity increase. While Raman amplification is likely the most cost-effective solution, it offers the lowest capacity increase. The E-band upgrade tends to be less disruptive due to the 14 THz guard band between the C- and E-bands. However, achieving the same capacity as the C+L-band system with Raman amplification requires additional band filters at the amplification stages and more interfaces, increasing the overall cost. Finally, the S-band upgrade provides the highest capacity increase, potentially at the same cost as the E-band upgrade, but it also increases the contiguous bandwidth used for data transmission. This can complicate network management and amplify the magnitude of power transients due to link faults.

Next, we compare the performance of transmission systems with Raman amplification. The S+C+L-band+Raman system stands out as the best in terms of total capacity, offering a 39.5% increase over the C+L-band+Raman system. Both E+C+L-band+Raman systems show similar capacities, showing a 32.8% increase

Fig. 2. (a) Optimal non-dominated solutions. Raman pump power distribution for the E+C+L-band system using the (b) div-pump and (c) group-pump strategies. (d) The network-wide average capacity for the different transmission systems.

Fig. 3. (a) Lightpath GSNR variation between fault and baseline scenarios and (b) the accumulated number of surviving lightpaths disrupted by the power transients caused by a link fault.

with respect to the same reference system. Noteworthy, the capacity gain of the S+C+L-band system over the E+C+L-band system decreases from 10% to 5% when Raman amplification is considered.

Figures 2b and 2c show the power levels of the Raman pumps for the two E+C+L-band systems (div-pump and group-pump) at an average $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 0.5$ dB. The optimization algorithm converges to solutions with low power allocated on pumps between the C+L and E bands to prevent power depletion in the E-band, which would otherwise reduce total capacity. This explains why both optimization strategies for the E+C+L-band system with Raman amplification resulted in similar Pareto fronts.

The network-wide average capacity in the Telefónica network, illustrated in Fig 2d, indicates that band upgrades without Raman amplification result in a smaller capacity increase. Integrating the S- or E-band into the C+L-band system diminishes the system's spectral efficiency. Consequently, the capacity improvement from band upgrades is small for longer links, despite the higher channel count enhancing the single-span ideal capacity.

Finally, Fig. 3a illustrates the variation in lightpath GSNR resulting from a single link fault across different lightpath frequencies. These were obtained by simulating every possible link failure and re-computing the GSNR of every lightpath that does not traverse the failed link. As can be seen, in the S+C+L system, the L- and S-bands are more affected than the C-band due to significant power transfer induced by the SRS effect between these two bands. The maximum GSNR reductions in the L, C, and S bands are -4.7 dB, -1.4 dB, and -6.8 dB, respectively. Importantly, the guard band between the C+L and E bands effectively reduces GSNR variation in the E+C+L-band system, with reductions of only -2.2 dB, -1.4 dB, and -0.3 dB for the L-, C-, and E-band, respectively. These observations suggest that using the E-band instead of the S-band results in a more transient-robust high-capacity network. To gain further insight, Fig. 3b shows the cumulative number of lightpaths that failed due to transients caused by faults in each link (i.e., the number of surviving lightpaths that have a GSNR below the threshold as a result of the power transient). The number of failed lightpaths due to a single link fault is significantly higher in the S+C+L-band system due to the greater number of SRS-interdependent channels.

4. Conclusion

This study evaluated the effectiveness of upgrading a C+L-band system by incorporating either the E-band or the S-band, using both lumped and hybrid amplification methods. The findings indicate that while the E+C+L-band system offers a slightly lower total capacity, it enables simplified network planning and operation and offers enhanced robustness to power transients.

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